

DETERMINATION OF MANUFACTURING DISTORTION IN LAMINATED COMPOSITE COMPONENTS

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SUMMARY: Manufacturing distortion of composites has been a problem for many years. Previous efforts have shown these distortions to be related to differences in the in-plane and through-thickness properties. Often tooling is modified to attempt to compensate for these fabrication induced distortions; however, the sources of the problem have not been clearly shown. Earlier efforts have suggested that both the cooldown from process temperature and shrinkage during cure play a role, yet no single work has measured the relative contributions of these effects. Further, researchers have suggested numerous other factors as being responsible for all, or some portion, of the measured distortion. In this work, distortion in autoclave-cured composite specimens has been experimentally measured, at temperatures ranging from 24°C to 178°C, to determine the reversible and irreversible contributions to manufacturing warpage. The measured reversible response closely matches computed distortion, based solely on the in-plane and through-thickness coefficients of thermal expansion. Further, it seems that the irreversible contributions can be separated into material dependent effects, such as cure shrinkage, and process related effects, such as part/tool interactions. Calculations indicate that both temperature change and cure shrinkage contribute significantly to manufacturing distortion; but, their contribution does not account for the total distortion. Trends in the experimentally observed distortion indicate the presence of other process related contributions.

KEYWORDS: distortion, warpage, composites manufacture, part/tool interaction

INTRODUCTION

Advanced composite materials are being used in an increasing variety of applications, ranging from sporting goods to aerospace components. However, difficulties in manufacturing and associated manufacturing costs are often strong deterrents to widespread industrial implementation. Autoclave processing is a proven source of high performance, reproducible composite parts; yet, with many years of process development, difficulties continue to arise during the creation of complex composite parts requiring a precise, specified shape. In curved composite “angle brackets”, manufacturing distortion results in a change in included angle that is often referred to as “spring-in”.

Manufacturing distortion results from the internal balancing of process-induced residual stresses [1] and can be severe, leading to out-of-tolerance dimensions and rejected parts or even difficulty extracting the part from the tooling [2]. This distortion has been suggested to be primarily related to differences in the composite material properties and responses in the

in-plane and through-thickness directions [3,4,5]. Examples of components where “spring-in” has been measured include wing leading edges [6], U-channel cross-sections [7], and waveguides [3].

Since, once cured, the resulting component geometries do not match the tooling geometry manufacturers often find it necessary to shape the tooling in an iterative fashion. This iteration of the tooling can be costly, and if material or laminate design is subsequently changed, the non-net shape tool will not generate shape correct parts. Other approaches have also been used to minimize warpage; however, many of the currently employed solutions do not directly address the causes of distortion. This can be attributed to an incomplete understanding the problem or to not recognizing the problem. Many factors enter into the final distortion; yet, little work has attempted to measure and separate the various contributions. Thus, the present project is specifically aimed at quantifying the factors that affect warpage to aid in the overall understanding, and development, of design practices which overcome manufacturing distortion, or at least that can lead to accurate predictions of required tooling geometry.

COMPONENTS OF MANUFACTURING DISTORTION

Manufacturing distortion can be seen in many types of fiber reinforced composites, with the properties of the constituent materials and the type of cure generally governing the severity. One of the worst cases is an autoclave cured carbon fiber/epoxy composite due to the low coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) in the longitudinal direction of the reinforcing fiber, a much larger CTE in the transverse direction and a large temperature difference between cure and room temperature. Many factors must be considered in solving the problem of manufacturing distortion. Anisotropic thermal contraction and cure shrinkage of the epoxy matrix are two commonly cited factors affecting warpage. While anisotropy of the laminate coefficients of thermal expansion is generally accepted as a major contributor to warpage, acceptance of other contributions, including anisotropy of cure shrinkage, is mixed. In some studies, cure shrinkage has not been considered in warpage predictions [2,8]. In other studies, it is believed to dissipate through viscoelastic relaxation during the curing process [1,9], and in still other research cure shrinkage is considered a significant contribution [4,5,10,11,12]. Further contributing factors that have been briefly studied are tooling material properties [13] interactions between the tool and the composite [13,14], fiber misalignment [8,15], and fiber volume fraction gradients [15,16]. To satisfy an apparent need to resolve the factors affecting manufacturing distortion, an experimental approach has been taken in this work to quantify the various contributions. These contributions have been categorized into two principal components: thermoelastic (reversible) CTE contributions, and non-thermoelastic (irreversible) cure and manufacturing contributions.

Thermoelastic Component

The thermoelastic component represents the reversible thermal expansion and contraction of the angle bracket specimen, which leads to its changing included angle. This component has also been referred to as shape instability, as this thermal expansion driven phenomenon continues to affect the component shape throughout the service life [4]. Previous research efforts have shown manufacturing distortions to be related to differences between in-plane and through-thickness properties of laminated composites, and closed-form equations have been developed to predict the thermoelastic change in shape for simply curved composite

laminates [2,3,4,5]. The initial and final geometries for an angle bracket corner are depicted in figure 1 showing how a change in thickness without a change in arc length must result in a change in included angle. This distortion does not occur in conventional materials since isotropic thermal expansion results in a uniform change in size.

Figure 1: Composite angle bracket geometries before and after cure [17]

For an anisotropic material, such as a laminated composite, it has been suggested that this thermoelastic distortion can be predicted from a knowledge of the initial specimen geometry (included angle), the coefficients of thermal expansion and the change in temperature. The relationship that has been developed is: [5]

$$\Delta\theta = \theta \left[\frac{(\alpha_I - \alpha_T)\Delta T}{(1 + \alpha_T\Delta T)} \right], \quad (1)$$

where;

- θ = angle bracket included angle,
- $\Delta\theta$ = change in included angle,
- α_I = in-plane coefficient of thermal expansion,
- α_T = through-thickness coefficient of thermal expansion, and
- ΔT = change in temperature.

This relationship assumes that the in-plane properties are quasi-isotropic and that the through-thickness properties are uniform throughout the laminate.

Non-Thermoelastic Component

The non-thermoelastic component of manufacturing distortion is a “one time only” contribution that occurs during fabrication and is irreversible. Many factors may contribute to the non-thermoelastic component, such as cure shrinkage, tooling expansion, part/tool interactions and factors associated with the manufacturing technique. In previous work [4,5], it was suggested that fabrication shrinkage could be accounted for in an extension of equation (1) by including an additional term:

$$\Delta\theta = \theta \left\{ \left[\frac{(\alpha_I - \alpha_T)\Delta T}{(1 + \alpha_T\Delta T)} \right] + \left[\frac{(\phi_I - \phi_T)}{(1 + \phi_T)} \right] \right\}, \quad (2)$$

where; ϕ_I = in-plane fabrication shrinkage, and
 ϕ_T = through-thickness fabrication shrinkage.

If fabrication shrinkage values for the constituent materials are available, anisotropic composite fabrication shrinkage values can be obtained from a micromechanics approach. This would allow the addition of a predicted cure shrinkage induced non-thermoelastic contribution to the already developed thermoelastic prediction. This additional term can be thought of as another factor contributing to the thickness change indicated in figure 1. Again, since the reinforcing fibers constrain the in-plane displacements, the through-thickness change is the major contributor to distortion. However, additional process related effects that may be encountered, such as volume fraction gradients [16], part/tool interactions or non-uniform curing [14], are not modeled by equation (2) since phenomena control which are not directly related to differences between in-plane and through-thickness properties.

EXPERIMENTAL MEASUREMENT OF DISTORTION

Angle Bracket Specimens

Carbon fiber/epoxy angle brackets were autoclave-processed at 178°C on aluminum convex tooling. Three repetitions of each specimen, investigating stacking sequence, laminate thickness and corner radius, were produced on tooling with a 90° included angle. The stacking sequences are referenced with 0° along the angle bracket axial direction and 90° following the curvature around the angle bracket corner. Figure 2 shows two cured test specimens, of different corner radii, resting on a section of aluminum tooling.

Figure 2: Angle bracket specimens on aluminum tooling showing “spring-in”.

Experimental Procedure

A laser rotation technique is used to measure the included angle as a function of temperature. The technique requires mounting the angle bracket specimen by one arm in the heated

chamber with a small mirror attached to each arm. The laser is aimed through the chamber glass door at the mirror on one arm and the resulting reflection is aligned with the reference mark on the projection screen. The specimen is then rotated until the reflection from the second arm aligns with the reference mark. The shaft rotation is electronically measured by an encoder and the included angle is determined. This measurement is repeated in the reverse direction to bring the specimen back into its original position and allow a second check of each measured included angle. Using this approach, measurement of specimens with included angles ranging from 30° to 180° can be accomplished. One pulse of the encoder corresponds to less than 0.02° and the reproducibility of measurement is on the order of ± 1 pulse.

Angle bracket specimen measurements were made at room temperature (24°C) and then at elevated temperatures on all angle bracket specimens evaluated. Each specimen was measured with the rotation technique in roughly 14°C temperature increments to 122°C. Following this, one specimen from each group was re-measured to 178°C in a similar fashion to check the linearity of the thermoelastic response at temperatures approaching cure. Once the maximum temperature was reached, measurements were repeated back down to room temperature to observe the repeatable, thermoelastic response of the angle bracket. A complete measurement of a single specimen could be completed in 5-6 hours, with most of the time involved in temperature stabilization for each angle measurement. The rotation technique simplifies the measurement of thermoelastic response, without sacrificing precision or accuracy, and allows the included angle to be measured directly at the desired temperature. A conceptual view of a specimen prepared for measurement and a photo of an actual specimen mounted in the chamber are shown in figure 3.

Figure 3: Rotation technique enables direct included angle measurement.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effects of stacking sequence, laminate thickness and corner radius on distortion were investigated by measuring the changing included angle, of specimens representing each variable, with temperature. Results for each effect investigated are plotted as graphs of “spring-in” angle versus temperature. The slope of the line on this type of chart is a measure of the thermoelastic contribution, while the offset from zero, at a reference temperature near the cure temperature, is essentially the non-thermoelastic contribution. Thus, the “spring-in” angle on the left side of the chart indicates the total room temperature distortion that would commonly be measured during a quality check. The value of “spring-in” on the right side of the chart is the contribution to the distortion that is not related to cooldown from cure [17].

Stacking Sequence Effects

As is seen in figure 4, both thermoelastic and non-thermoelastic components contribute to the overall warpage of angle brackets. However, their absolute and relative contributions vary, depending on stacking sequence. All specimens of this stacking sequence comparison were 8 ply and have a 6.4 mm corner radius to minimize other possible distortion variable interaction. Most of the laminates show similar thermoelastic response based on the slopes, $\Delta\theta/\Delta T$, which vary only slightly and are roughly $0.003 \text{ deg}/^\circ\text{C}$. The $[(0)_8]_T$ and $(0/+30/0/-30)_S$ laminates show much lower thermoelastic response due to large in-plane CTE's in the 90° direction, which correspond closely to the through-thickness CTE values. These more similar in-plane and through-thickness thermal expansions result in distortion behavior resembling that of an isotropic material, with a thermoelastic coefficient, $\Delta\theta/\Delta T$, of approximately $0.0005 \text{ deg}/^\circ\text{C}$. This large difference in thermoelastic response is predicted by equation (1) as both the in-plane and through-thickness CTE's are affected by changing ply orientation [4,5]. All of the laminates show a significant non-thermoelastic contribution (on the right ordinate), ranging from about 0.7 - 1.2 degrees. This large contribution to the room temperature distorted shape accounts for roughly 65% of the total room temperature distortion for the majority of the specimens. For the $[(0)_8]_T$ and $(0/+30/0/-30)_S$ laminates the contribution approaches 90% of the total. Using equation (2), the distortion related to cure shrinkage can be estimated and compared to the total non-thermoelastic distortion measured.

Figure 4: Experimental Stacking Sequence Effects

To investigate the relationship between predicted cure shrinkage contributions to distortion and the total non-thermoelastic distortions measured for these specimens, material properties representative of T300/934 [16] were applied in equation (2). Three dimensional (3-D) laminate properties were determined for each laminate [16], based on the T300/934 data, and the results were inserted into equation (2) along with an assumed 0.5% matrix cure shrinkage. Results for the crossply and quasi-isotropic laminates were the same, with a predicted thermoelastic contribution of $0.0036 \text{ deg}/^\circ\text{C}$, or approximately 0.56 degrees of “spring-in” at room temperature. The contribution to “spring-in” in these crossply and quasi-isotropic laminates is predicted to be approximately 0.32 degrees, based on 0.5% cure shrinkage. Thus, for these specimens, the combined predicted thermoelastic and cure shrinkage contributions sum to only approximately 50% of the total measured room temperature distortion.

Predictions of the distortion contributions, using equation (2) and the same 3-D properties, can be also be performed for the other laminates. For example, for the (0/+30/0/-30)_S laminates the predicted thermoelastic contribution is 0.0012 deg/°C, or approximately 0.19 degrees of “spring-in” at room temperature. Again, based on the 0.5% cure shrinkage, the contribution to “spring-in” for this stacking sequence is predicted to be approximately 0.11 degrees. For this stacking sequence, which is expected to respond in a more isotropic fashion due to less difference between the through-thickness and in-plane properties, the total predicted “spring-in” at room temperature is only about one third that of the crossply laminates of this investigation. Comparison of these predictions with the experimental results indicates that roughly 0.5 - 0.6 degrees of “spring-in” measured at room temperature remains unaccounted for. Matrix cure shrinkage as high as 1.5 - 2.0% would be necessary to account for the total measured non-thermoelastic distortion; however, this value of shrinkage seems extreme. Based on the measured differences in the non-thermoelastic contribution for changing stacking sequence it is believed that a significant portion of this contribution must be related to manufacturing variables. To further investigate deviations from the predictions of equation (2), which would indicate non-thermoelastic contributions other than cure shrinkage, measured effects of corner radius and laminate thickness are presented.

Radius Effects

Radius is not predicted, by equations (1) or (2), to be a contributor to either thermoelastic or non-thermoelastic distortion. No significant variation in thermoelastic response is measured, as seen by the nearly identical slopes in figure 5, which have $\Delta\theta/\Delta T$ values of approximately 0.0045 deg/°C for these 16 ply specimens. However, it is significant that while the slopes are similar for the various radii, the relative offsets vary, indicating that the measured non-thermoelastic component is radius dependent. It seems that the larger the corner radius, the less process effects other than cure shrinkage contribute to the non-thermoelastic distortion. This is consistent with a cause, such as local corner thinning during processing, which would be expected to be less severe for larger radii.

Thickness Effects

Increased thickness has often been expected to stabilize the distortion of composite parts. Results of these tests indicate that the thermoelastic component of distortion is little affected by thickness, which follows from equations (1) and (2). However, the thinnest laminates tested (8 ply, or 1 mm) show the least thermoelastic effect. This may be explained by the fact that these 8 ply specimens can also be the most difficult to measure due to their low stiffness which results in the highest potential for specimen flexure from the cantilevered mounting geometry. What does seem to match intuition is that the thickest specimens do show less total room temperature spring-in, but the experimental results indicate that the difference is primarily driven by the non-thermoelastic component of distortion. Again, this difference in non-thermoelastic contribution is not predicted by equation (2) and therefore must be assumed to be related to process effects other than shrinkage during cure.

Figure 5: Corner Radius Effects on Spring-In

Figure 6: Effect of thickness on manufacturing distortion

General Discussion

In addition to the three variables shown in detail in figures 4 - 6, preliminary tests of included angle variations indicate a decreasing thermoelastic slope with increasing included angle. Further, these preliminary results indicate that the non-thermoelastic component also varies with included angle. These trends are both consistent with the predictions of equations (1) and (2). Overall, experimental results for these carbon fiber/epoxy angle brackets do seem to point out that the thermoelastic variations follow the trends predicted in equations (1) and (2). As predicted by equation (2), cure shrinkage should respond to the same variables as the thermoelastic component. However, from this set of experimental data it seems that the total non-thermoelastic contribution is not following the trends predicted. This leads to the belief that more than one factor determines the non-thermoelastic contribution, and that contributors other than cure shrinkage take on different functionality.

Future efforts are planned to investigate the effect of varying the fiber type while maintaining the same matrix material. This should allow further separation of some of the processing effects from the cure shrinkage. Further, tooling material comparisons are under way to evaluate the effect on part/tool interaction, and fabrication experiments are planned to attempt to continue to break down the non-thermoelastic contributions.

CONCLUSIONS

“Spring-in” of carbon fiber/epoxy angle bracket specimens has been experimentally measured to determine the thermoelastic (reversible) and non-thermoelastic (irreversible) components of distortion. A technique, incorporating a laser source, was used to obtain precise measurements of the included angle of specimens at temperatures ranging from room temperature to 178°C. The data collected indicate that all of the specimens respond linearly and in a repeatable fashion to temperature change. Differences between the measured thermoelastic contribution and the tooling geometry allow the remaining non-thermoelastic contribution to be separated. Relative non-thermoelastic contributions were computed for the stacking sequence specimens and found to range from approximately 65% to 90% of the total room temperature “spring-in”. Only the angle brackets with the largest corner radius and greatest thickness showed lower relative amounts of non-thermoelastic distortion. For an assumed matrix cure shrinkage of 0.5% the “spring-in” was predicted to be only a little more than half of the thermoelastic contribution. While this is a significant amount of the total specimen distortion, it is far less than the total non-thermoelastic contribution experimentally measured.

Trends in thermoelastic response, $\Delta\theta/\Delta T$, with stacking sequence variation were predictable, based on closed-form relationships. The measured independence of thermoelastic response on changing corner radii also matched predictions. However, the varying non-thermoelastic contributions for different radii were not predicted. As specimen geometry changed with increasing corner radius, non-thermoelastic contributions decreased, indicating sources of manufacturing distortion other than a predictable cure shrinkage induced non-thermoelastic contribution. Results related to thickness variations also indicate similar distortions not directly attributable to shrinkage during cure. Thus, these trends further suggest that process related contributions to the final distorted shape can be significant and that such other non-thermoelastic effects are not predicted by the closed-form relationships based solely on differences between in-plane and through-thickness properties. Further investigation of the

details of these other contributors is necessary to be able to fully predict distortion during cure.

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